

Appendix S1: List of papers included in the systematic review.

References in **red text** were excluded from the meta-analysis due to insufficient detail being provided regarding estimates of uncertainty, figures not depicting the treatments of interest, or biomass being presented as percent regrowth.

(Balog et al., 2017; Batool et al., 2022; Bennett & Bever, 2007; Bernaola & Stout, 2019, 2021; Borowicz, 1997, 2009; Brunner et al., 2015; Caccavo et al., 2022; Charters et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2022; Contreras-Cornejo et al., 2021; Cosme et al., 2016; Coy et al., 2019, 2020; Currie et al., 2011; Dabré et al., 2021; de Bobadilla et al., 2017; Du et al., 2022; Eichholtzer et al., 2021; Forlano et al., 2022; Frew et al., 2020; Gan et al., 2017; Gange et al., 2002; He et al., 2017; Kabaluk & Ericsson, 2007; Kula et al., 2004; Metwally et al., 2022; Orians et al., 2018; Prischmann-Voldseth et al., 2020; Raglin et al., 2022; Real-Santillán et al., 2019; Rivera-Vega et al., 2022; Selvaraj et al., 2020; Tao et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2022; Whyle et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2021; Zeng et al., 2022; Zitlalpopoca-Hernandez et al., 2017)

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